

EFFECT OF THE TEMPERATURE AND SALINITY ON ACTIVE METABOLISM OF *MUGIL PLATANUS*.

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INTRODUCTION

The metabolism of a fish includes three well-differentiated levels: standard metabolism, routine metabolism and active metabolism. The standard metabolism is the minimum energy required for the fish to survive, associated to rest and unfed state. The routine metabolism is the fraction of energy used by unfed fish with movement of spontaneous swimming, or routine activity. Routine metabolism is the mean rate oxygen consumption measured when precautions are taken against the fish being influenced by outside stimuli (1). The active metabolism already represents the metabolic rate in the maximum level of activity. BRETT (2) demonstrated that fast swimmer fishes can increase its metabolism up by 10 times the standard metabolism, whereas fish of colder waters increase its metabolic rate by 2 or 3 times. In addition, the swimming performance (3) was recorded as the highest position-maintaining velocity plus the fraction of the time interval of the velocity in which they became exhausted (4), i.e., the physical capacity that facilitates it to swim against a certain water direction during a certain period of time (5).

This study aimed to investigate the effect of the temperature (25° C, 20° C and 15° C) and salinity (35‰, 20‰ and 5‰) on active metabolism of *Mugil platamus* (mullet), a eurihialinic and eurithermic fish..

METHOD

To quantify the active metabolism of the fish in activity, an swim tunnel was built and used in our laboratory, based on the descriptions of BRETT (2) and modified for individuals of small size. The swim tunnel consists of a metabolic chamber placed inside of a box with water, to help in the maintenance of the temperature. The fish was forced to swim against a current produced by a propeller attached to variable-speed electric motor. Each fish was allowed to adjust and orient itself in the chamber at a low water velocity. The speed of the current was measured through a "Venturi" meter flow type. A water sample was then taken and the outlets and inlets was closed.. At the end of the forced-swimming period, the water velocity is greatly reduced and a water sample was collected. To guide the flow and define the swimming space, flow laminators were installed in the two extremities of the metabolic chamber. The swim tunnel total volume was 1, 2 liter.

Before the beginning of the experiments, the animals were maintained in the active respirometre (swim tunnel) with a continuous water circulation during at least 90 minutes to attenuate the management stress. Then, the water supply was suspended and the active respirometre was closed, so that the fish could consume the present oxygen in the known water volume for a period of an hour. The active respirometres were protected by an antepar to isolate the animals from possible moves in the laboratory. The difference between the oxygen concentrations, determined at the beginning and at the end of the confinement, was used to calculate the consumption during the period. To minimize the effect of the low oxygen concentration and the metabolits accumulation on the metabolism, the experiments duration was regulated so that the oxygen concentration by the end of experiments was larger than the 70% of its initial concentration. The dissolved oxygen was determined through the Winkler method.

After 90 minutes. the speed was, then, slowly increased (1cm/s) until reaching 15 cm/s (\pm 0.31), so that the fish was forced to swim in that speed for one hour. The flow was monitored during the whole period of the experiment and the concentration of dissolved oxygen in the swim tunnel was determined in the beginning and in the end of the experiment, using the Winkler's method. The total oxygen consumption in each experiment was calculated by the difference between the initial and final concentration. To minimize the effect of the low oxygen concentration and the metabolits accumulation on the metabolism, the experiments duration was regulated so that the oxygen concentration by the end of experiments was larger than the 70% of its initial concentration. The difference between the oxygen concentrations, determined at the beginning and at the end of the confinement, was used to calculate the consumption during the period. Immediately after each experiment, the total length and the wet weight of the tested animals were measured. No fish was used twice. The processing and charting of the data were accomplished with aid of a spreadsheet, adapted to this work. The average specific consumption of oxygen by the mullet (routine and active metabolism) were tested, using ANCOVA, ($p < 0,05$) analysis.

RESULTS

For the acclimated mullet to the 25° C temperature, the specific oxygen consumption increased in the three employed salinities. We checked that the specific oxygen consumption of fish from the acclimated control group to 25° C temperature (table 1), subjected to 35, 20 and 5 salinities were, as a rule, 4,22 mlO₂/Kg/min, 4,04

mlO₂/Kg/min, 4,34 mlO₂/Kg/min, respectively. These values represent a metabolic level enhancement of 216,7%, 181% and 185,4% in relation to the temperature 15°C.

The specific consumption of the acclimated fishes in the salinity of 5 (table 1), to the temperatures of 25° C; 20° C and 15° C were respectively 2,34 mlO₂/Kg/min, 3,70 mlO₂/Kg/min and 4,34 mlO₂/Kg/min as a rule.

Comparing these results with the highest salinity 35, the oxygen specific consumption decreased to 1,92 mlO₂/Kg/min, 3,16 mlO₂/kg/min and 4,22 mlO₂/Kg/min, representing an oxygen consumption decreasing in relationship with the salinity 35 of 85,4%; 86,7% and 4,34 % respectively.

DISCUSSION

Some teleost fishes can bear a wide salinity variation and live well among the sea, river water and brackish (estuary water). These movements are usually associated with the fish cycle of life, for example, the mullets (*Mugil platanus*) that lay eggs in the sea and in alevine phase. They can be found in small rivers of sweet water and brackish. When they arrive into maturity, these fishes come to the sea water to reproduce. The passage from an environment to another requires deep changes into the osmoregulator process, as a consequent energy waste. The osmoregulation in estuary teleost fishes is done mainly by the gills which also participate in the gases changes. The secretion of salts by the epithelium gills needs to be done by active transportation because it occurs from a minor blood concentration to a bigger one of the surrounding environment, when the fish is in salty water. This fact would lead us to think that the more the mullet penetrates into the salty water, the more would be the oxygen consumption resulting from energetic waste to keep the homeostese. The same would occur, in case the mullet penetrated into fresh water where the blood concentration would be bigger than the surrounding environment one. In the estuary fish *O. niloticus*, the costs of osmorelation calculated in relationship with the minor oxygen consumption obtained to 11,5 of salinity were of 19 in the salinities of 0, 7, 5 and 22,5 and of 29 to 30 of salinity (6). PARRY (7) observed that in young Atlantic salmon, *Salmo salar* the passage from the sweet water to the sea water successive dilution, provoked alterations, not only in the survival rate, but also in the osmotic regulation, depending on the weight, influencing in a more accentuated way the smaller specimens. For both authors, however, the explanation would be the same, that is, the existence of a bigger relation volume-surface in the young and consequently a bigger gill area per weight unit would make with the smaller fishes were subjected to a bigger osmotic stress due to the bigger water and salts capture.

Although the marine fishes swallow sea water, the swallowing rates measures reveal that only a small fraction of the sodium total capture comes from the water swallowing; the biggest influx part of this ion occurs in other place, presumably because the gills are permeable anyway. Either through the body general surface or through gills, it is sure that the fishes adjusted to the sea water are relatively permeable to the ions and the ones adjusted to the sweet water are relatively impermeable (8).

The salinity influence on the oxygen consumption of the studied mullets was not evidenced in the groups under control, in the three tested salinities 5; 20 and 35, that is, there was no statistical difference among the control group averages. Many surveys have shown that the salinity variation has a small effect on the salty water fishes respiration (8). Studies held with *Lagodon rhomboides* for CALDWELL (9) showed that this fish is indifferent to salinity. However, it is used to laying its eggs in estenohaline waters. *Lagodon rhomboides* has been found in sweet water (10) and also in hypersalt water of 75 ppt of salinity. The nature eurhaline of *L. rhomboides* makes the energy waste to the ionic and osmotic regulation small (10). This also seems to be the case of the mullet, taking into account the non statistical significance between the control group averages in different salinities, not only for the active metabolism, but also for the routine metabolism. However, for the sweet water fishes, the situation is different in researches held with *Phoxinus erythrogaster* and *Fundulus catenatus* with the salinity increasing from 0 to 10, there was an increasing of 30% and 40% of the oxygen consumption respectively (11). The salinity seems not to affect the mullet metabolic rates. We did not find out any difference among the controlled groups in the three employed salinities either from the active metabolism. The mullets active metabolism was minor for the acclimated specimens samples to the salinity of 20. For the active metabolism, there was also a minor tendency of the oxygen specific consumption for the acclimated mullets to the 20 salinity. This salinity can be closer to the value that this animal is adjusted in this phase of its life, that is, alevine, perhaps due to this, the oxygen consumption was reduced and the swimming time up to the exhaustion was bigger when compared to the other used salinities.

Focusing on autoecology, the temperature affects the biochemical and physiological processes that involve since the digestion till the locomotion. The temperature changes also influence the food intake and the predators escape, in this case, it would be affecting the balance between the prey survival the predator capture success (12), resulting in a change mechanism in the species geographical distribution (13). The temperature variability is extremely important for the ecology. A temperature that flows between 10° C and 20° C with an average of 15° C does not present the same effect on the organisms that have a constant temperature of 15°C (14). The temperature changes have considerable effects on several physiological processes. In limits, the temperature elevation accelerates most of the vital processes. In general, an elevation of 10° C in the temperature causes an increasing from 2 to 3 times the oxygen consumption rates. In this research, it is easy to take the effect on most

employed temperature (25°C) on the mullet oxygen consumption rate, that is an adjusted expression of an animal metabolic activity. For the used mullets as control, at the highest temperature, there was a tendency to the oxygen specific consumption increasing, but it was not significative. However, at the highest temperature (25°C), it was checked a significative increasing of the mullet metabolism. BATTY et al. (12) studying the temperature effect on the escape reply of the fish larvae *Clupea harengus*, it was verified a straight relation among the temperature increasing and the speed decreasing and the swimming capacity of these larvae. The temperature is an environmental factor that can, according to FRY classification (1), affect the organisms in a lethal, controlled, disguised or directing way depending on the time and/or stimulus intensity, spacial extension of this influence and the organism capacity to be adjusted to termical variations. LEITE (15) studying *Xenomelaniris brasiliensis* in three temperatures (28°C, 23°C and 18°C) verified that in salinity 34, the temperature had a pronounced effect on the routine metabolism increasing when the temperature raised from 23°C to 28°C. The oxygen consumption increasing when the temperature raised from 18°C to 23°C, in spite of being smaller, it was significative too. The results obtained in this research indicated that the active metabolism of mullets increases in the salinity of the 35 in the three temperatures. The significant increase in the consumption of oxygen should probably be, as one of its factors, due to problems caused by alterations of the energy metabolism.

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Table 1 - Oxygen specific consumption (mlO₂/Kg/min) of the mullets active, acclimatated in different salinities and temperature. Between parenthesis, pattern desviation; each value represents the average of 5 determination.

Salinity	Temperature 15 ⁰ C	Temperature 20 ⁰ C	Temperature 25 ⁰ C
	Specific consumption	Specific consumption	Specific consumption
5	2.34 (±0,26)	3,70 (±0,95)	4,34 (±0,38)
20	2,22 (±0,16)	3,00 (± 0,53)	4,04 (±0,50)
35	1,92 (±0,09)	3,16 (±0,45)	4,22 (±0,28)

